

interview transcript (Brand business profit target)

Interviewer: AA

Interviewee: SA (Footwear brand Director)

Interview Setting: Interview conducted in footwear factory meeting room.

The interview was conducted at 17:00 PM on Friday afternoon.

Affiliation with interviewee: Chief of Footwear Brand.

(Summary draft of Interview)

Interviewer : For customer loyalty, brand awareness and after-sales service network product positioning brand business profit target ?

Interviewee : Loyalty programs are an effective technique to retain customers by giving them special status. It includes establishing a reward system based on the services or products you provide.

Relationship advantages and exclusive experiences: They may be relevant to the client's industry - such as attending exclusive professional events or providing them with a dedicated consultant, etc.

Other benefits of choosing loyal customers might be offering them membership in a VIP club or sending them invitations to sporting or cultural events, etc.

Interviewer : Favorable contract conditions ?

Interviewee : You can offer your customers discounts based on the duration of the contract without commitment, for example by giving them free access to premium content. This type of reward enhances the sense that customers made the right decision by choosing your company because they feel like they are saving money.

Interviewer : Offer tailored incentives for your client's industry ?

Interviewee : By adding exclusive services to the program, you're demonstrating your ability to support your clients. This type of incentive can take the form of legal assistance, marketing advice, service subscriptions, free testing of new materials, training, exclusive access to technical content, and more. These benefits should be tailored to specific industry and customer needs to ensure their relevance.

Interviewer : Brand business profit target ?

Interviewee : Targeting your most profitable customers is a common strategy for increasing sales revenue. Some customers will contribute more to your profit margin than others. The key is to identify those customers early and adapt your sales strategy accordingly. For example, you may want to: set higher sales targets for your best customers, find similar products or services to sell them find similar customers to sell to.

Interviewer : Methods for selling more to your best customers ?

Interviewee : You can try the following ways to sell more to your best customers:

up-selling - selling them premium products with higher profit margins

cross-selling - offering complementary products to those already sold

diversifying - identifying a need and developing new products/services to meet them

Interviewer : Find new profitable customers ?

Interviewee : You can try to expand your customer base by targeting new customers who fit a similar profile to your existing best customers. Use market research and market reports to gain knowledge about your marketplace, your customers and their behaviour to target them better.

Interviewer : Professional access, focusing on high-end target customers

Acknowledge that you have a specific target audience ?

Interviewee : It's important to understand that your products and services have a target audience that can be defined. As a marketer, your primary goal is to find ways to identify who these people are so that you can create marketing campaigns that speak to them directly.

Interviewer : Determine what criteria you intend to use to identify the consumers you most wish to reach ?

Interviewee : An audience can be sorted any number of ways based on an almost infinite number of criteria. But your audience is unique to your brands, so you're going to want to identify the factors that can be used to create a better connection between their potential needs and what your company offers.

For starters, are there some demographic points that you can use such as age, gender or geography to begin to refine who the best recipients are for your products? How about criteria that matches a prospect's beliefs, opinions, attitudes or intentions with your marketing message?

The goal of this step is to eliminate the people for whom an offer won't be relevant or important. With these people out of the mix, you can now focus your marketing messages to reach the remaining people who are most apt to be interested and willing to take some sort of action when they come in contact with your marketing message.

Interviewer : Identify what your customers and prospects want most from you ?

Interviewee : One of the challenges that most marketers face is that they are too close to their own brands. While you certainly want to promote your brands and services in a positive light, you also need to be willing to put yourself in the shoes of your target customers as often as possible. Chances are they don't know much about your brand or understand the benefits you offer nearly as well as you do. By seeing your brand through new eyes, you can also look for potential weaknesses, areas of potential misuse or misunderstanding, and even things that consumers may object to or find offensive.

Taking this step better allows you to create marketing messages and campaigns that fully address possible brand concerns and objections before they occur.

Interviewer: Thanks for your time.

Interviewee: You are welcome.